

THE EFFECT OF ALKALOID MEDICINAL VEGETABLES ON THE HUMAN ORGANISM

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Abstract: This article describes the fact that alkaloids are nitrogen-containing organic compounds, their occurrence in plants in nature, their positive and negative effects on the human body, the optical activity of alkaloids, the importance of its various representatives on an industrial scale.

Keywords: N-oxide form, tubocurarin, morphine, strychnine, colchicine, cocaine, quinine, Plaun family, mydriatic effect, galenic and new drugs, Compositae, lobelin, optical activity.

Alkaloids are found readily in plant tissues. Most of them are toxic. Alkaloid is the Latin word for alkaline-alkaline oides. Alkaloids are natural nitrogen-containing organic compounds that are basic in nature, have a complex structure and unique properties. Occurs in plants in 3 different forms:

1. In pure (basic) condition;
2. In the form of compounds-salts combined with acids;
3. In the form of N-oxide oxidized by the nitrogen atom.

They are mainly synthesized by plants. Plants belonging to the family of legumes, poppies and lilies are rich in alkaloids. The effects of alkaloids on animals and humans have been shown to be extensive. Some dilate blood vessels and increase blood circulation (atropine), increase skeletal muscle tone (strychnine), or to a lesser extent (tubocurarine), relieve pain (morphine, cocaine), dilate the pupil (atropine) or compresses (pilocarpine), accelerates respiration (lobelin).

Due to the medicinal properties of alkaloids, it has led to the synthesis of many drugs: the synthesis of cocaine-like substances led to the production of novocaine, the production of quinine-specific substances was the basis for the production of acricine. A number of morphine-specific substances have also been synthesized. Synthesis of alkaloids has shown that artificial methods require large sums of money and complex tools, so plants themselves are still a source of alkaloids.

Alkaloids are mainly grown in hot and some cold parts of the earth, mostly in hot and humid tropical countries. Alkaloids are found in the Plaur family (plaurbaranes), less common in cereals and osoka plants.

Alkaloid-rich plants include tulips, lilies of the valley, tulips, roses, celery, amaryllis, legumes, and lilies of the valley. In plants, alkaloids occur in the form of salts dissolved in the cell. Its content can range from a few thousandths to a few percent, with 15 to 20% occurring in the bark of a henna tree. In some plants, alkaloids are found in all organs (common krasavka-belladonna and Caucasian type), and most are concentrated in a single organ. Often, different organs of the same plant contain different amounts of alkaloids, and some of their organs may be non-alkaloid, for example, poppy - only the seeds do not contain alkaloids. It is rare for a single alkaloid to be found in a plant. The alkaloids found in a single plant are often similar. Simple alkaloids occur in different families, complex alkaloids (colchicine, cocaine, quinine), on the contrary, occur only in a certain plant and cause its main feature. Studies have shown that if the Compositae plant family contains 1,000 species, it contains up to 10 species (1%) of alkaloids. Interestingly, one of them is very high in alkaloids of the genus Senecio. Alkaloids are found in plant organisms and often have strong physiological properties. The selection of alkaloid plants is based primarily on the knowledge of the local population and then adapted to their botanical counterparts. Alkaloids begin to accumulate in seeds, roots, and bark during the growing season. Therefore, they are more abundant in mature seeds than in unripe seeds. Depending on their function, alkaloids

accumulate at different times during the growing season. The amount of alkaloids can change with changes in ecological and geographical conditions, as well as during the growth of a single plant in different conditions. It is important to determine the maximum possible time before collecting the alkaloid. Most alkaloids have optical activity. The isolated anabazine, ephedrine, salcoline, garmalin, safocarpine are widely used in medicine and in the national economy.

Alkaloids play an active role in plant ontogeny. When growth is strong (before flowering), the highest amount of alkaloids is found in the leaves and stems, while during flowering, their amount in these organs decreases and increases in the flowers. During fruiting, the alkaloids in the flowers decrease and increase in the fruits.

In the industrial use of alkaloids, it was found that the amount of alkaloids in a plant varies depending on the place of growth and the season. In the spring, the alkaloids are low, and the maximum amount occurs at the time of flowering, and then decreases again. However, there are exceptions to this rule, such as the triacontin alkaloid in the newly opened leaves of the gledichia tree, which was found to disappear after 10 days.

Tests have shown that morphine is present in the milky liquid in the flower box, but not in the leaves, stems and seeds. Caffeine is found mainly in coffee beans, nicotine in tobacco leaves, and quinine in tree bark. Painkillers and drugs (morphine, codeine), strong central nervous system stimulants (strychnine, brucin), mydriatic effects (ie, dilation of the pupil), products (atropine, giostiamine) and miotics (i.e. eye pupil). Some alkaloids have adrenergic activity, stimulate the sympathetic nervous system, stimulate the heart and increase blood pressure (ephedrine, epinephrine). Others lower blood pressure (reserpine, protoveratrin A). Due to their strong physiological activity, many alkaloids are used in medicine despite being a potent poison. In folk medicine, green twigs are prepared in the form of drops and used in rheumatism, gastrointestinal diseases and toothache.

Some of the green twigs were used to make bitter drinks, and the fruit was used to make syrups. Alkaloids are the most valuable of the medicinal substances used in medicine. They are often widely used in the treatment of various diseases because of their specific and irreplaceable effects with other drugs. About 80 alkaloids are currently used in medical practice. They come in pure form, in the form of galenic and freshly prepared drugs, and in the form of many complex preparations.

In short, the biologically active substances found in plants are essential for life. Their main source is plants. The effects of alkaloids on the human body vary. They are useful and important for the proper growth and development of young children and to enhance the metabolic processes in the body of the elderly. All of the above compounds play a role in human life. These compounds enter the human body only in food. Insufficient or complete absence of these compounds in the diet can lead to various diseases. In medicine, alkaloid-containing plants are widely used in medicine.

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